

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI TRANSPORT VAZIRLIGI
TOSHKENT DAVLAT TRANSPORT UNIVERSITETI**

**“TURKIY DAVLATLARNING O‘ZARO MANFAATLI
INTEGRATSIYASI – BARQAROR TARAQQIYOT
KAFOLATI”**

II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya

MATERIALLARI TO‘PLAMI

Toshkent, 2025-yil 2-3-may

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UDK:

**“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot
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“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to‘plamida jami 94 ta ilmiy maqola kiritilgan bo‘lib, mazkur maqolalar Turkiy davlatlar o‘rtasidagi iqtisod, siyosat, madaniyat, turizm sohalaridagi hamkorlik va imkoniyatlar, Barqaror kelajak uchun suv resurslarini boshqarishda iqlim o‘zgarishining roli, o‘rta asr Markaziy Osiyo allomalari ilmiy merosining uchinchi renessans poydevorini barpo etishdagi ahamiyati, Turkiy davlatlarda transport, muxandislik kommunikatsiyalari, energetika, logistika, turizm sohalaridagi integratsiya jarayonlari, Turkiy davlatlar o‘rtasidagi raqamli transformatsiya, fan, ta‘lim va innovatsion rivojlanish istiqbollari kabi yo‘nalishlarni ilmiy jihatdan ochib berilishiga qaratilgan. To‘plamda o‘zbek, rus, ozarbayjon, ingliz tillarida tayyorlangan maqolalar mavjud. Ushbu konferensiya to‘plamidan transport, iqtisodiyot, falsafa, pedagogika va tarix yo‘nalishidagi tadqiqotchilar keng foydalanishi mumkin.

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“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta‘lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligining 2024-yil 27-dekabrda “2025-yilda xalqaro va respublika miqyosida o‘tkaziladigan ilmiy va ilmiy-texnik tadbirlar rejalarini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”gi 490-son buyrug‘i hamda Toshkent davlat transport universiteti rektorining 2025-yil 23-apreldagi 108-U sonli buyrug‘i asosida tashkil etildi

ETHICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE USE OF TELEMEDICINE AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROVISION OF MEDICAL CARE

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Abstract. Healthcare is one of the key areas of social policy that directly affects the quality of life of the population. In the context of modern challenges, such as the growth of chronic diseases, the aging of the population and the need to introduce innovative technologies, the reform of the healthcare system is becoming especially relevant. In Uzbekistan, with its rapidly developing economy and demographic changes, modernization of the medical sector is necessary to ensure accessibility and quality of medical care for all citizens. The article examines the ethical and legal aspects of the use of telemedicine to ensure the protection of patients' rights and data security.

Keywords: healthcare, digital technologies; patient, telemedicine, privacy, database, health, risk, side effects, treatment.

Аннотация. Здравоохранение является одной из ключевых сфер социальной политики, непосредственно влияющей на качество жизни населения. В условиях современных вызовов, таких как рост хронических заболеваний, старение населения и необходимость внедрения инновационных технологий, реформирование системы здравоохранения становится особенно актуальным. В Узбекистане, с его стремительно развивающейся экономикой и демографическими изменениями, модернизация медицинской сферы необходима для обеспечения доступности и качества медицинской помощи для всех граждан. В статье рассматриваются этические и правовые аспекты применения телемедицины, чтобы обеспечить защиту прав пациентов и безопасность данных.

Ключевые слова: здравоохранение, цифровые технологии; пациент, телемедицина, конфиденциальность, база данных, здоровье, риск, побочные эффекты, лечение.

THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY: In recent years, digital technologies have become an integral part of healthcare, providing new opportunities for diagnosis and treatment. Telemedicine and mobile applications have changed the approaches to interaction between doctors and patients, improving the availability of medical care and increasing the level of self-control over the state of health. In this article, we will look at the impact of these technologies on diagnosis and treatment, their advantages and challenges. The purpose of this study is to analyze the planned reforms in the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2025, assess their focus and potential impact on improving medical care for the population.

METHODS AND MATERIALS: Studies of the state support provided to the healthcare sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan over the years of independence have shown significant improvements in its regulatory framework: the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Health Protection" (dated August 29, 1996 No. 265-I), the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the protection of reproductive Health of Citizens" (dated March 11, 2019), Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.UP-5590 dated December 7, 2018 "On comprehensive measures to radically improve the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan", No.UP-6110 dated November 12, 2020 "On measures to introduce fundamentally new mechanisms into the activities of primary health care institutions and further improve the effectiveness of ongoing reforms in the healthcare system", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.PP-5199 dated July 28, 2021 "On measures to further improve the system of specialized medical care in the field of healthcare" and No. PP-140 dated 05/01/2023 "On additional measures to digitalize the healthcare system".

The latter provides for the creation of digital healthcare and software development. To finance the project "Support for healthcare Digitalization reforms", Uzbekistan and KfW Bank signed a loan agreement in the amount of 45 million euros for a period of 12 years, including a five-year grace period, as well as a grant agreement in the amount of 5.5 million euros.[1]

The study used official documents and statements from the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as publications in leading national media such as "Gazeta.uz ", "Gift", "Kun.uz " and "Prezident.uz". The methodological base of the study includes an analysis of regulatory legal acts, policy documents and statistical data, as well as a comparative analysis with international practices in the field of healthcare.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: Health care financing In 2025, it is planned to allocate 41 trillion soums for the development of health care in Uzbekistan, which is 14.3% more compared to the previous year. These funds are aimed at creating new hospitals, expanding existing medical facilities and increasing the volume of preventive examinations.

Implementation of public health insurance

One of the key areas of reform is the phased introduction of the state health insurance system. In 2025, pilot projects will start in several regions of the country. Free medicines for common diseases will be available by electronic prescription.

An effective primary care system will be implemented, queues are converted to electronic format, and dental services are partially transferred to the private sector. Advanced training and motivation of healthcare professionals. Salary increases and the introduction of performance bonuses are expected. More than 30 thousand specialists will be trained in Uzbekistan and abroad. Modernization of medical infrastructure. Multidisciplinary clinics, laboratory centers are being created, control over the equipment is carried out through an electronic system. Creation of the Center for Medical Projects.

The project office will be responsible for introducing insurance, improving the quality of services, developing medical science and the private sector.

The development of the field of medicine is under the close attention of our state. A number of state programs were adopted in the republic, including the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 11.09.2023, No. UP-158, which was responsible for the process of digitalization of all sectors of the economy, etc. and medicine. [2,4]

The Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan, within the framework of the project of state support for digital reforms in the healthcare sector, has developed a plan to digitalize the activities of medical institutions for 2022-2026. Based on this document, the priority area is the creation of an ICT infrastructure for connecting to the Internet and computerizing medical preventive institutions (LPU), pharmacies and health authorities. [3]

In 2025, 41 trillion soums will be allocated for the development of health care. It is also envisaged to create a "unified electronic platform" for monitoring population health indicators. as priority digital health interventions

An analysis of the current state of Uzbek medicine in 2020-2023 showed a significant increase in the potential of medical institutions (Table 1.)

Table 1.

The main indicators of the development of the field of medicine in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Unit indicators	Unit of measurement	years				
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2023 in % by 2020

Number of hospital facilities	units	1232	1281	1328	1432	116
The number of hospital beds is	thousands of beds	153	161	170	175	114
Number of doctors of various specialties	thousand people	92	93	98	104	113
Number of secondary medical staff	thousand people	366	370	378	388	106
The volume of services rendered is	trillion.sum	3,4	5,1	6,6	8,6	2.5 times more

As can be seen from the table, positive results have been achieved in the republic for all the studied indicators. An analysis of the performance indicators of Uzbek medicine over the past three years has shown the stable development of this area.

The use of digital technologies in medical institutions will create a single platform where information about patients and their treatment results will be posted from all clinics. In the future, the platform may become a single base for ongoing scientific research.

To the question of what is telemedicine? - we can say, that telemedicine covers various types of remote medical services, including video consultations, remote patient monitoring, and physician training. It allows for diagnosis and treatment without requiring the physical presence of the patient.

Advantages of telemedicine.

- Accessibility: Patients can receive consultations regardless of their geographical location, which is especially important for residents of remote areas.
- Time saving: Minimizing travel time and waiting in queues.
- Reducing the burden on medical facilities: Doctors can serve more patients in a short time.

Disadvantages and challenges.

- Problems with communication quality: An unreliable Internet connection may interfere with the quality of consultations.

- Data security: The risk of confidential information leaks.

Lack of personal contact: Lack of physical interaction can reduce trust between doctor and patient.

Health Monitoring Applications.

Types of applications There are many mobile applications aimed at health monitoring, from fitness trackers to programs for monitoring the condition of chronic diseases [11].

Advantages of using.

- Individualized approach: Patients can monitor their health in a convenient mode.
- Awareness Raising: Apps help people better understand their condition and increase motivation for a healthy lifestyle.

Limitations and challenges

- Data reliability issues: Not all applications provide accurate and scientifically sound data.
- Security: Storing personal data may pose a threat in case of unauthorized access.
- Dependence on technology: The emergence of dependence on mobile devices can have a negative impact on health. [6]

Research shows that telemedicine can increase patient satisfaction and improve clinical outcomes. For example, according to recent studies, 85% of patients using telemedicine services noted the high quality of care received. In addition, statistics show an increase in the use of mobile health apps, with an increase of 25% over the past three years.

The future of digital technologies in medicine promises many opportunities. The integration of artificial intelligence can significantly improve diagnostics, and the development of wearable devices will make it possible to more effectively monitor health status in real time. However, with the growth of technology, the need to adhere to ethical standards and protect the rights of patients is also increasing.

1. Wearable devices and real-time monitoring.

Wearable technologies such as fitness trackers and smartwatches allow patients to track their health in real time. These devices can monitor your heart rate, blood sugar levels, and other important parameters, transmitting the data to doctors for further analysis.[6]. This not only improves patients' self-control, but also allows doctors to respond more quickly to changes in their condition.

2. Personalized medicine

The development of genomics and DNA sequencing technologies opens up new horizons for personalized medicine. Doctors will be able to develop individual treatment plans based on the unique genetic characteristics of each patient. This will increase the effectiveness of treatment and reduce the risk of side effects.[7].

3. To protect your data

With the increasing use of digital technologies, the need to protect medical data is also increasing. Blockchain can provide secure storage and transfer of data, ensuring that information remains confidential [5] and protected from unauthorized access.

4. Ethical and legal aspects

With the development of technology, new ethical and legal issues arise. The need to comply with confidentiality, data protection, and patient consent standards is becoming particularly urgent. Medical institutions and technology developers should work to create standards and regulations to ensure the safe use of new solutions.

Exploring the prospects for the development of digitalization of the medical field, we came to the conclusion that the essence of innovation is to create an extensive base for scientific research, compile reliable statistics, identify areas of medicine that need more funding and improvement [6]. However, the issue of solving ethical problems remains open as a result of the digital reforms of the industry, which can be grouped into the following aspects:

The practice of the COVID-19 pandemic has shown the need for joint active participation of the state, medicine and the population in compliance with hygiene standards. In these conditions, the development of legal norms of health, such as the interests of children[9], public health, and the right of persons at risk, was much more relevant;

contradictions of ethics and law with the development of medical technologies, the rights of test-tube children and the problem of "extra embryos", the rights of subjects of reproductive technologies and objects of application, the right to life and rejection, including the right of a doctor to refuse and protect risk.[8];

Digitalization of healthcare is also dangerous due to the creation of big data on medical information at the national, regional and small population levels, which can lead to the loss of professional authority by doctors.;

a decrease in the activity of the population in maintaining their health, which is not solved by ICT technologies. It is important for attending physicians to promote a healthy lifestyle for their patients, including creating incentives for citizens to eat healthy.[7], give up bad habits, and play sports of all age categories.

The main indicator of the sustainable development of a civilized state is the health of the nation.

CONCLUSION: Digital technologies such as telemedicine and mobile apps are playing an important role in transforming the healthcare system. They make medical care more accessible and personalized, but they require a careful approach to safety and quality issues. For the successful implementation of these technologies, it is necessary to take into account both the advantages and the challenges they bring.

Digital technologies, including telemedicine and mobile applications, play a key role in the transformation of the healthcare system. They increase the availability of medical care by improving the interaction between patients and doctors and providing a more personalized approach to treatment. At the same time, the use of these technologies entails a number of challenges related to data security, quality of medical services and lack of personal contact. [10] Ultimately, the successful implementation of digital technologies in medicine requires an integrated approach based on scientific evidence, ethical principles, and a commitment to improving the quality of life for patients. This will ensure not only the improvement of medical services, but also the creation of a safer and more efficient healthcare system for future generations.

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